

Structural Elucidation of Ziracin, a Novel Antibiotic which is Active against Organisms Resistant to Methicillin and Vancomycin^ψ

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Ziracin¹ (1) is a member of the everninomicin² group of antibiotics and is highly active against Gram-positive bacteria including methicillin resistant *Staphylococci* and vancomycin resistant *Enterococci*. Ziracin is undergoing extensive clinical trial and a few preliminary available results suggest that ziracin is safe and effective. If successful in the larger scale clinical investigation, then ziracin will become one of the major new antibiotics to be used in the human medicine in the next couple of decades.

diazomethane, everninomicin D₁ (3) underwent smooth cleavage to yield olgose (4) and the methyl ether of everninonitrose pyranosyl(1→4)digitolactone (5). Elucidation of structures of the lactone⁴ (5) and olgose⁵ (4) have been presented from our laboratories in greater detail elsewhere and will not be presented in this review. The linkage of 5 to 4 in the structure of methyl ether of everninomicin D (6) was deduced as follows. Everninomicin D (2) on exhaustive methylation yielded permethylated everninomicin

Ziracin (1)

Ziracin has been described in the literature¹ as antibiotics 13-384 component 1 and also as Sch 27899. It is produced by *Micromonospora carbonacea*. As mentioned above, ziracin is related to everninomicins²⁻⁴, the structures of which were elucidated several years ago in our laboratory. Before a detailed description is made regarding the structural elucidation of ziracin, it will be useful to briefly summarize the structural elucidation of everninomicin D³ (2), the first member of this class of complex antibiotics, the structure of which was elucidated in our laboratory. The detailed description is referred to the citations under Ref. 3.

Everninomicin D (2) is a colorless crystalline solid, C₆₆H₉₉O₃₅NCl₂ (MW 1537), m.p. 169–171°. In the infrared it showed absorption for hydroxyl, ester and nitro (1555 cm⁻¹) groups. The structural elucidation of everninomicin D (2) involves hydrolysis under acidic conditions, determination of structure and stereochemistry of the various components and finally assigning the sequence in which they are linked. Thus everninomicin D (2) (C₆₆H₉₉O₃₅NCl₂) on hydrolysis with aqueous acid yielded everninomicin D₁ (3), C₆₆H₁₀₁O₃₆NCl₂. On treatment with

D (7). On solvolysis, 7 yielded a mixture of products from which 8 and 9 were isolated. As we know from the structure of olgose⁵ (4) that the two hydroxyl groups in the lyxose portion (ring H) of the molecule in 4 are linked with the side-chain (10), it is clear therefore that the other two hydroxyl groups in the evermycose portion of the molecule 4 must be involved in linkage with the lactone carbonyl of 5 in the structure of methyl ether of everninomicin D (6). Based on all these observations we have assigned structure 2 to everninomicin D in which stereochemistry of all the asymmetric centres have been assigned excepting at C₁₆.

Ziracin¹ (1) is an amorphous solid, C₇₀H₉₇NO₃₈Cl₂, ν_{max} 1540 cm⁻¹ (nitro), [α]_D -47.2°. Molecular weight of ziracin is established to be 1629 based on high resolution FAB mass spectrometry. We have studied extensively FAB mass spectrum of everninomicin D (2) and compared it with that of ziracin (1) and concluded that (a) the above two antibiotics have identical composition and sequence of A, B and C rings; (b) the E ring in ziracin (1) has an extra hydroxyl group and (c) the H ring in ziracin has a hydroxyl group compared to a methoxyl group in everninomicin D (2) and the substitution pattern at C₅₂ in the

^ψ Dedicated to Professor T. R. Govindachari for his 80th birthday. This paper was written for the International Conference on "Frontiers in Biotechnology" held at Trivandrum in 1997.

two compounds are different.

Accurate mass measurement indicated that the group attached at C_{52} in compound 1 to be $C_8H_7O_4$ (m/z 167) and based on 1H nmr spectra (as will be discussed later) it appeared to be a 2,4-dihydroxy-6-methylbenzoyloxy residue. Results of the high resolution FAB mass spectral data of some important ions of 1 are summarized in Fig. 1. As has been reported earlier, these compounds fragment at the central orthoester generating two sets of fragment ions which are easy to recognize; one set shows chlorine isotopes and the other set of ions contains no chlorine. As one would expect, in chemical degradation experiments, 1 be-

has very similarly to everninomicin D (2). Thus when a methylene chloride solution of 1 was stirred with 0.1 *N* HCl, it yielded 11 which when treated with diazomethane underwent cleavage to yield the lactone 5 and compound 12. The lactone (5) was found to be identical with the one obtained from everninomicin B, C and D. Single and two-dimensional 400 MHz nmr data of 5 showed the C_{18} hydroxyl to have equatorial stereochemistry, which is the opposite of what we reported in an earlier work³, based on an assumption, from ir data, of a boat conformation for the lactone ring in 5. In compound 1, strong NOESY connectivity among the 17, 19 and 21 protons, plus the two diaxial

Ziracin

Everninomicin D (2)

Fig 1

couplings ($J_{18,19} = J_{19,20} = 8$ Hz) demonstrate a chair conformation and arabino stereochemistry for ring C. In a subsequent publication⁶ it has also been suggested that the stereochemistry of H18 be revised. Compound 12 is an amorphous solid, $C_{43}H_{64}O_{25}$ (m/z 980.3832), $[\alpha]_D -46.9^\circ$ (chloroform), $\lambda_{\text{trifluoroethanol}}$ 242 (22231), 261 (11099), 278 (5223), 294 nm (2970), ν_{max} 1735 cm^{-1} (ester). ^1H nmr spectrum of 12 showed the presence of two methyl doublets (δ 1.31, 1.33), a tertiary methyl (δ 1.2), an aromatic methyl (δ 2.5), five methoxyl groups, four anomeric hydrogens (δ 5.31, 4.27, 4.96, 4.78), two aromatic hydrogens (δ 6.33), and H_{52} appeared at (δ 5.43) as a doublet of a triplet and the large coupling constants ($J_{51,52} = J_{52,53a} = 9.7$ Hz; $J_{52,53e} = 5.8$ Hz) would suggest H_{52} to be in an axial orientation. In compound 12, C_{23} appeared at δ 71.1 compared to δ 45.8 for oligose⁵ (4), indicating a hydroxyl substitution at that carbon. Also in compound 12, C_{45} appeared at δ 72.5 compared to δ 80.5 in 4. This indicates that the C_{45} methoxyl group in compound 4 which appeared at δ 58.4, is replaced by a hydroxyl substituent at that position in compound 12. The ^1H nmr spectra of 12 and 4 showed the expected similarities and differences. For ex-

ample, characteristic singlets for H_{54} were present in both the compounds at δ 5.14 and 5.22. In compound 12, H_{52} appeared at δ 5.43 as a multiplet and two-dimensional nmr connectivity experiments demonstrate its axial-axial couplings with H_{51} and H_{53} . As in 4, H_{50} and H_{51} in 12 are both axial. Hydrolysis of 12 in methanol and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid yielded 13 and 14.

The mass spectral data of 13 showed ions corresponding to 15 at m/z 133 and 16 at m/z 161. When the ^1H nmr and ^{13}C nmr spectra of 13 are compared with evertetrose B^7 (18) striking similarities become apparent. The difference between the two compounds is the absence of the signal for the C_{45} O-methyl group in 13. This is consistent with all the observations made so far in nmr and ms of 1 and 12. Thus compound 13 must be 45-des-*O*-methyvertetrose B. To verify the structure further and also to assign the absolute stereochemistry of 13, it was methylated with methyl iodide in the presence of sodium hydride and dimethyl sulphoxide. Permethylated compound (17) thus obtained was found to be identical in all respects [nmr, mass spectra, $[\alpha]_D -61.8$ (CHCl_3)] when compared with permethylated evertetrose B^7 . The structure and absolute

stereochemistry of evertetrose B (18) has been rigidly established by us in an earlier publication⁷.

The structure of compound 14, oil, C₁₇H₂₂O₉ (*m/z* 370.1255; calc. 370.1264) has been assigned based on nmr and high resolution mass spectral data, and correlation with the data published on olgose side-chain (10)⁴. Upon methanolysis of compound 1, compound 19 was isolated which on treatment with diazomethane yielded 14. Compound 19, C₁₅H₁₈O₉ (*m/z* 342.0942) showed an aromatic methyl at δ 2.50 (d, $J_{60,62} = 1$ Hz), two *meta*-coupled aromatic protons at δ 6.23 (H₅₈, $J_{58,60} = 2$ Hz) and 6.19 (H₆₀, $J_{58,60} = 2$ Hz and $J_{60,62} = 1$ Hz), a carbomethoxyl group at δ 3.80, two methylene dioxy protons H₅₄ at δ 5.03 and 5.24 ($J = 0$ Hz), H₅₀ at δ 4.51 ($J_{50,51} = 5$ Hz) and H₅₁ at δ 4.47

($J_{51,52} = 5$ Hz). ¹³C nmr spectra of 19 and 14 also verify the structures assigned to these compounds. Compounds 13 and 14 were derived by methanolysis of 12 and as we have argued in an earlier publication during the structural elucidation of olgose (5), we concluded that 12 is derived by the loss of methanol between the -CO₂Me and C₅₃ hydroxyl group in 14 and the hydroxyls at C₄₆, C₄₇ in 13 forming an orthoester linkage in 12. This, as in the case of olgose, would explain the presence of -CO₂Me in 14 and an orthoester in 12. As mentioned, mild acidic hydrolysis of 1 yielded 11 which underwent cleavage with diazomethane to yield 5 and 12. This sequence of reactions parallels chemical degradation of other everninomicins². It has been pointed out already that 1 has two orthoester carbons,

- (13) R = H; R¹ = OMe; R² = OH
 (17) R = Me; R¹ = R² = OMe
 (18) R = H; R¹ = R² = OMe

- (14) R = CH₃
 (19) R = H

(20) $R^2 = R^3 = H$; $Y = Z = OH$

(24) $R^2 = Ac$; $R^3 = Me$; $Y = Z = OAc$

(25) $R^2 = R^3 = H$; $Y = H$; $Z = OMe$; $Y' = OH$; $X' =$

(21) $R^2 = R^3 = H$; $Z = OH$

(22) $R^2 = Ac$; $R^3 = Me$; $Z = OAc$

out of which one belongs to compound **12**. The second orthoester is opened to a hydroxy ester in **11** under acidic conditions and during the diazomethane reaction the newly formed hydroxy ester moiety is cleaved to give **5** in which the phenolic hydroxyl group is methylated and compound **12** in which two phenolic hydroxyl groups are methylated. In **11**, a new ester carbonyl group is formed and it lacks the presence of one of the orthoester carbons of **1**. We propose, therefore, that the combination of this ester carbonyl group at C₁₆ with the hydroxyl groups at C₂₄ and C₂₀ of **11** results in the formation of the second orthoester carbon in the structure of **1**.

An unique structural feature shared among the everninomicins including zirconin is the presence of two acid-sensitive orthoester linkages³ at C₁₆ and C₄₉, the former being relatively more acid-labile. The absolute configuration of C₄₉ center was determined by X-ray crystallography⁵ and the stereochemistry at C₁₆ was unequivocally deduced⁸ via a novel acid-catalyzed orthoester isomerization as follows.

When a solution of zirconin (**1**) in anhydrous THF was treated with *p*-nitrobenzoic acid under refluxing conditions, a mixture of **20** and **21** along with some zirconin was obtained. The mixture was separated by column chromatography on silica gel to yield **20** as major product (20 : 21 = 5 : 1). Prolonged heating shifted the product ratio in favor of **21** (20 : 21 = 1 : 3).

Compound **20**, [α]_D -49.4 (CHCl₃, *c* 1.035), is a colorless amorphous solid which has the same molecular composition and similar fragmentation pattern as zirconin, C₇₀H₉₇Cl₂NO₃₈ (M + Na, HRFAB found 1652.4983, calc. 1652.4963). All proton and carbon resonances were assigned¹⁰ using ¹H nmr, ¹³C nmr, HMQC, HMBC and HMQC-TOCSY spectra. Examination of the nmr data of

compound **20** against those of zirconin (**1**) reveals that the significant changes in chemical shifts involve only rings, C, D and E. Specifically, major shifts occurred at H17, H25, H27 and C16, C17, C24, C25 (Table 1). However, the coupling constants among protons in rings C-E remained unchanged. More importantly, the two characteristic ¹³C nmr signals at δ 119.20 and 119.24 ppm confirm the presence of two orthoester carbons. The NOE experiments provided key information on the configuration of the C₁₆ center. The NOE cross-peak observed in the NOESY spectrum of **20** between H17eq in ring C and H27 (methyl) in ring E indicates that these protons are *cis* with respect to the dioxolane ring D; such NOE is absent in zirconin (**1**). While NOE between H17eq and H25 (or H18) was observed in zirconin, it was inconclusive due to the overlap resonances of H25 and H18 (since NOE is expected between H17/H18); no NOE was found between H17 and H25 in **21**. Our findings of NOE differences are consistent with that observed with the synthetic C-E disaccharide fragments⁹.

Upon mild two-phase acidic hydrolysis (0.1 N HCl aq./ EtOAc, 1 : 4 v/v), **20** was converted to the same ester **11**, obtained earlier from zirconin. Although the same hydrolysis product was obtained from both zirconin and **20**, the rate of hydrolysis for **20** (29 h, 50% conversion) was much slower than that for zirconin (**1**) (7 h, 100%). Further treatment of **11** with diazomethane afforded lactone **5** and olgose-like compound **12**. These degradation products were fully characterized and found to be identical with the degradation products obtained from zirconin. Putting together all the evidence presented above, we propose that compound **20** is the C₁₆ stereoisomer of zirconin (**1**). In addition, NOE evidence cited above for both zirconin (**1**) and **20** establishes⁸ the absolute stereochemistry at C₁₆ for both zirconin (**1**) and **20**.

This novel isomerization is presumably achieved via an acid-catalyzed ring opening of D-ring to form the oxonium ion intermediate (**22**) and subsequent ring closure from either face of the ring C to give both zirconin and **20**. Isomer **20** is thermodynamically more stable, and therefore, it accumulates in the reaction mixture.

Compound **21**, [α]_D -54.3 (CHCl₃, *c* 100), a colorless amorphous solid, has the same molecular formula, C₇₀H₉₇Cl₂NO₃₈ (M + Na, HRFAB found 1652.4967, calc. 1652.4963) and mass spectral fragmentation patterns as the parent antibiotic. It is slightly more polar than **20**. Assignments of proton and carbon resonances by extensive nmr experiments unfolded a similar phenomenon found in **20**, i.e. major changes in chemical shifts are within C-E rings, and to a less extent at C/H30, C/H31. The changes are more substantial than those in **20**. The largest shifts in nmr occurred at C₂₃ ($\Delta\delta$ = 6.4 ppm) and C₂₄ ($\Delta\delta$ = 3.6 ppm),

TABLE I—NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS IN COMPOUNDS **1**, **20**, **21** (in ppm)

Position	Sch 27899 (1)		20		21	
	¹³ C	¹ H	¹³ C	¹ H	¹³ C	¹ H
16	120.40		119.24		118.71	
17	39.79	1.81, 2.41	40.43	1.99, 2.24	40.00	1.96, 2.29
18	68.16	3.93	68.38	3.88	68.53	3.83
19	88.18	3.07	88.10	3.06	88.20	3.03
20	70.05	3.84	69.43	3.75	68.90	3.76
21	17.77	1.25	17.84	1.28	17.86	1.25
22	101.02	5.03	101.49	5.01	98.49	5.03
23	72.95	4.08	72.75	4.08	79.35	4.11
24	80.50		81.93		84.06	
25	78.45	3.93	76.11	4.12	76.48	3.44
26	68.80	3.82	68.53	3.81	71.44	3.29
27	18.80	1.35	18.96	1.22	16.59	1.38

H_{25} ($\Delta\delta = -0.49$ ppm) and H_{26} ($\Delta\delta = -0.53$ ppm) suggesting change at C_{23} position in the formation of **21** from ziracin. ^{13}C nmr resonances at δ 118.71, 119.20 ppm again indicate the presence of two orthoester carbons.

Acid hydrolysis of **21** under the same biphasic conditions³ was very slow and the C_{49} orthoester hydrolyzed first. Both **20** and **21** were derivatized via methylation with diazomethane followed by acetylation with excess acetic anhydride. The products were again characterized by extensive nmr experiments. Based on chemical shift changes of the relevant methine protons upon acylation, it is evident that compound **22**, the peracetylated derivative of the methyl ether of compound **21**, possesses an acetoxy function at C_{25} but not at C_{23} , an indication of the fact that in compound **21** C_{25} -hydroxyl is free and C_{23} -hydroxyl group is tied up in the orthoester linkage.

Consistent with the assignment of structure **20**, compound **24**, the peracetate of the methyl ether of compound **20**, showed acetylation at 23-OH but not at 25-OH. The hydroxyl group at C_{23} being in close proximity participates in the ring closure of the intermediate **23** to give a new orthoester **21**. In 2D-NOE spectrum of **21**, the presence of crosspeak between H_{17eq} and H_{23} is consistent only with the stereochemistry depicted in structure **21**.

To test the generality of this orthoester isomerization, several related everninomicins were found to undergo similar rearrangement. Thus, everninomicin D (**2**), which lacks 23-OH, when subjected to the same isomerization conditions, yielded only one product, compound **25**.

The everninomicins and their isomers were tested in *in vitro* antibacterial assays against both methicillin-susceptible and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococci*, and vancomycin-susceptible and vancomycin-resistant *Enterococci*. Interestingly, while compound **21** showed virtually no activity, isomer **20** type compounds retained high antibiotic activities, even though they are slightly less potent than the parent antibiotic ziracin (**1**).

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